

Chronic kidney disease and its health-related factors: A case control study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a global health burden, affecting 843.6 million people (2017). Diabetes and hypertension are prevalent risk factors linked to CKD, in areas in demographic transition, like Kerala, India. **Objectives:** This study examined the relationship between CKD and specific health factors, including diabetes, hypertension, hypothyroidism, urinary tract infections (UTIs), family history of kidney disease, and cardiovascular diseases. **Materials and Methods:** A hospital-based case-control study was conducted at Pushpagiri Medical College Hospital, Kerala, India, from October 2023 to March 2024. The study included data collected from medical records of 100 CKD cases (GFR < 60 ml/min/1.73 m²) and 100 controls without CKD, analyzed using SPSS software. **Results:** Univariate analysis revealed significant associations between CKD and history of diabetes ($\chi^2= 15.126$, $p<0.01$), hypertension ($\chi^2= 31.202$, $p<0.01$), cardiovascular disease ($\chi^2= 17.195$, $p<0.01$), and family history of kidney disease ($\chi^2= 8.791$, $p<0.01$). Multivariate logistic regression showed that while the association between CKD and diabetes was insignificant (Odd's Ratio (OR)=1.668, CI: 0.832-3.344, $p=0.149$), significant associations were observed for hypertension (OR=5.255, CI: 2.512-10.993, $p<0.01$), cardiovascular disease (OR=2.336, CI: 1.112-4.909, $p=0.025$), and family history of kidney disease (OR=7.359, CI: 1.902-28.476, $p=0.004$). **Conclusion:** The study concluded diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disease and family history of kidney disease are risk factors for CKD in South Kerala, emphasizing the need for targeted public health interventions.

Keywords: Chronic Kidney Disease, Hypertension, Diabetes, Cardiovascular Disease, Hypothyroidism, Urinary Tract Infection

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Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) has emerged as one of the most prominent causes of death and suffering in the 21st century. The burden of CKD is estimated to be affecting about 10% of the population as per the 2024 statistics.¹ The actual numbers are not known particularly in the scenario where the burden of CKD from lower income countries is increasing. According to the International Society of Nephrology Global Kidney Health Atlas (ISN-GKHA) 2024 update, there are gaps in the reporting of data related to availability and access to essential treatment for CKD, and very low numbers of patients with kidney failure are able to access care in many countries of the world.²

Although the mortality associated with end stage kidney disease (ESKD) has decreased, global burden of disease studies has shown that CKD is a leading cause of deaths in the world. This may be due to the rise in associated risk factors like smoking, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus.³

The symptoms of CKD are often non-specific or not at all. Frothy urine, swelling under the eyes, swelling of the body, itching, frequent urination, lack of sleep, fatigue etc. are some of the symptoms that could herald kidney disease.⁴

As in other Lower Middle-Income countries, CKD is diagnosed late in India. Lack of awareness and the relative lack of symptoms are noted to be factors associated with the delayed diagnosis of the disease. Untreated CKD is an important cause of cardiovascular disease, leading to premature death and disability. The Indian cohort of CKD patients is younger than western counterparts, with a preponderance among male patients.⁵ Thus is erroneously thought to be a harbinger of death and dependence, but through proper support and management(secondary and tertiary prevention strategies), the outlook for patients can be improved⁶.

In rural Kerala, the prevalence of kidney disease has been estimated to be about 4.86% based on a study by S.P Haveri et al ⁷. Isolated studies show that CKD poses a huge burden on the health system of India due to the high prevalence of diabetes and hypertension in this region⁸.

About 25,000 patients are undergoing maintenance haemodialysis in Kerala. Since there is no CKD registry in the state, the extrapolated numbers of new patients with CKD every year is between 6000- 7000.⁹ Even though mortality has declined in patients with end-stage kidney disease (ESKD), uncontrolled CKD , which will need Renal Replacement Therapy in the forms of hemodialysis or renal transplantation, adds to the costs of healthcare in the state, which Kerala can hardly sustain¹⁰. There is a large, growing aging population in Kerala. The number of people with non-communicable diseases like diabetes mellitus and hypertension is also increasing in the state. The effects of climate change and changing temperatures of the state affect CKD patients in a disproportionate manner, necessitating the need for pre-emptive mitigation measures before the next heat wave strikes the state ^{11,12}. Despite these trends, CKD is rarely studied in Kerala or even India. Hence it is difficult for policy makers to gain a comprehensive understanding of the CKD burden to formulate effective policies to reduce CKD-related mortality and morbidity.

Thus, a case control study was conducted among CKD patients attending a tertiary care hospital in South Kerala to help stakeholders create policies and effective public health interventions to reduce the burden of this deadly disease in the most densely populated part of the globe.

The objectives of this case-control study were to identify and compare the risk factors associated with CKD, and investigate the influence of demographic and clinical factors on CKD as compared to non-CKD controls, among patients receiving care at a tertiary care hospital in South Kerala. The case-control design was chosen to explore the complex, multifactorial causes of CKD, in a resource efficient manner.

Materials and Methods

The STROBE Checklist for reporting observational studies was used to ensure methodological rigor, reproducibility, transparency, and completeness in all aspects of this case control study reporting. The checklist we used is attached to the supplementary files.

Study Design and Setting: A hospital-based case-control study was conducted at Pushpagiri Medical College Hospital, Kerala, India, from October 2023 to March 2024. A total of 100 cases and 100 controls were purposively selected from hospital medical records. Cases were identified based on an estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate (eGFR) below 60 ml/min/1.73 m², while controls had an eGFR above this cutoff. Both groups were matched for age and gender to minimize confounding.

Study Population:

- **Eligibility Criteria for Cases (n=100):** Patients diagnosed with CKD (eGFR <60 ml/min/1.73 m²), confirmed on two occasions at least three months apart using the CKD-EPI equation.(13)
- **Eligibility Criteria for Controls (n=100):** Patients attending the hospital for non-renal conditions, with no history or clinical evidence of CKD, confirmed by medical records and routine lab tests.

Case and Control Identification

- **Source:** Hospital medical records and laboratory test results.

- **Method:** Cases were identified using eGFR data calculated via the validated CKD-EPI equation, ensuring standardization. Controls were selected from patients with documented non-renal conditions.

Rationale

- **Cases:** Defined using rigorous diagnostic criteria to ensure the inclusion of clinically significant CKD cases.
- **Controls:** Drawn from the same healthcare-seeking population to reduce selection bias.

Matching Criteria

The study matched **cases** (n=100) and **controls** (n=100) based on the following criteria:

1. **Age:** Cases and controls were matched to ensure a comparable distribution of ages across both groups, reducing confounding effects of age-related factors on chronic kidney disease (CKD) outcomes.
2. **Gender:** Matching was performed to balance the proportion of males and females between the cases and controls, eliminating gender as a potential confounder in the analysis.

Identical diagnostic criteria and calculation methods (CKD-EPI) were applied to both cases and controls, ensuring comparability. By matching cases and controls, from the same hospital population, the study ensures that observed differences in outcomes or exposures are more likely to reflect true associations with CKD rather than confounding by these variables.

Sample Size

The sample size was calculated to detect an association between history of diabetes and CKD from a previous study by Ghelichi-Ghojogh et al¹⁵, taking percentage of history of diabetes in cases (P₁) as 48.3% and percentage of history of diabetes in controls (P₂) as 16.6%, with an alpha value of 0.05 (2- sided) and a power of 80%, the minimum required sample size (N) was estimated to be 34 for each group. The estimated sample size was 34 cases and 34 controls, but 100 participants were included in each group to enhance the study's power and reliability.

$$N = \frac{2 \times (z_{\alpha} + z_{1-\beta})^2 \times PQ}{(P_1 - P_2)^2}$$

$$= \frac{2 \times (1.96 + 0.84)^2 \times 32.45 \times 67.55}{(48.3 - 16.6)^2} = 34$$

$$P = \frac{P_1 + P_2}{2}, Q = 100 - P$$

Data Collection

Data were extracted from hospital medical records using a standardized collection sheet. (attached) Collected information included demographics, medical history, family history of kidney disease, and clinical/laboratory data (e.g., serum creatinine, blood pressure, and fasting blood glucose).

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Continuous variables were presented as means and standard deviations, while categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. To assess the unadjusted associations between risk factors and CKD, the Chi-square (χ^2) test was employed for categorical variables. Odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated to quantify the strength of association between CKD and potential risk factors. Adjusted associations were found using multivariable logistic regression, $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Outcomes, Exposures, Predictors, Confounders, and Effect Modifiers

1. **Outcomes:** The primary outcome was Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD), diagnosed using an eGFR < 60 ml/min/1.73 m², calculated based on serum creatinine levels using the CKD-EPI equation.
2. **Exposures:** Factors that may influence the development or progression of CKD. These factors included

- **Diabetes Mellitus:** Diagnosed by fasting blood glucose ≥ 126 mg/dL or HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$. Data source: medical records, fasting plasma glucose, and HbA1c test results from standardized hospital laboratory tests.
- **Hypertension:** Defined as blood pressure $\geq 140/90$ mmHg or use of antihypertensive medication. Data source: medical history and BP recordings from hospital records.
- **Urinary Tract Infection (UTI):** Diagnosed based on clinical records indicating symptoms (e.g., dysuria, cloudy urine) or confirmed bacterial infection. Data source: patient records.
- **Cardiovascular Disease (CVD):** Includes ischemic events such as myocardial infarction or stroke. Data source: documented clinical history.
- **Hypothyroidism:** Defined by clinical diagnosis in records, including symptoms like fatigue or weight gain.
- **Family History of Kidney Disease:** Identified through medical records documenting hereditary kidney disorders (e.g., polycystic kidney disease).

Lifestyle factors (e.g., smoking, alcohol use, nutritional history, lipid profile, physical activity) were excluded due to extraction of data from medical records and potential bias in self-reported data.

3. **Predictors:** Biochemical test results like serum creatinine, urea, albumin; demographic factors like age, gender, and socioeconomic status, medical history of cardiovascular disease, or family history of CKD. Source of Data: Laboratory reports from hospital records database.

Method of Assessment: Standardized automated laboratory equipment following hospital protocols, for all participants, ensuring consistency.

4. **Potential Confounders:** Factors that may distort the relationship between exposure and outcome, like age, gender, or socioeconomic factors. Source of Data: Hospital registration records. Uniform data collection methods ensured comparability across cases and controls.
5. **Effect Modifiers:** Variables such as the duration or severity of comorbidities, use of medications, and nutritional status were not included in this study due to limitations in the availability of reliable data. These variables required longitudinal data, patient interviews, or additional diagnostic evaluations, which were beyond the retrospective design of the study. Furthermore, the primary focus was to identify broad associations between key risk factors and chronic kidney disease (CKD), rather than to analyze the nuanced effects of modifying factors. Including such variables would have significantly increased the complexity and resource requirements of the study, potentially compromising feasibility within the given constraints.

6. Operational definitions of diagnostic criteria

- **Diabetes Mellitus:** Fasting Plasma Glucose ≥ 126 mg/dL or HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$ on two separate occasions. Random Plasma Glucose ≥ 200 mg/dL in symptomatic patients.
- **Hypertension:** Blood Pressure $\geq 140/90$ mmHg measured on at least two occasions. Use of antihypertensive medications.
- **Cardiovascular Disease:** Documented history of myocardial infarction, stroke, or other ischemic events.
- **Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD):** eGFR < 60 ml/min/1.73 m² confirmed on at least two occasions, 3 months apart.

7. Efforts to address potential sources of bias

1. **Selection Bias:** Matching cases (CKD patients) and controls (non-renal patients) on age, gender, using the same hospital data, helped ensure comparability and reduce confounding effects related to demographic factors. Clear definition of eligibility criteria for both cases and controls established rigor in the study.
2. **Information Bias:** A standardized data collection sheet was used for all participants to ensure consistency in data collection. The use of established tools and equations (e.g., CKD-EPI for eGFR calculation, calibrated hospital equipment for BP ensured objective and accurate measurements. Cross verification of patient data with the patients was not done because of the retrospective nature of the study.

3. **Recall Bias:** Reliance on objective medical records for exposure and comorbidity data reduced the dependence on participant memory.
4. **Confounding Bias:** Age and gender matching between cases and controls to mitigate for their potential confounding effects. Potential confounders (e.g., diabetes, hypertension, obesity) were identified and adjusted for during statistical analysis using multivariable regression models.
5. **Measurement Bias:** Consistent procedures were used for biochemical tests and BP measurements, for all participants and records were examined to reduce bias. The use of hospital records to gather these data would help reduce such bias.
6. **Observer Bias:** Data collectors(students) were trained in the study protocol to ensure uniformity in interactions and assessments.
7. **Attrition or Participation Bias:** Efforts were made to include as many eligible participants as possible to minimize non-participation bias.
8. **Reporting Bias:** The study adhered to the STROBE checklist to ensure comprehensive reporting of methods, results, and limitations. The study was reviewed and approved by an ethics committee, ensuring accountability and adherence to ethical guidelines.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Pushpagiri Medical College Hospital. Permission was also obtained from the Medical Records Department of the institution.

Results

A total of 100 cases and 100 controls were matched for age ($T = -0.986$, $p = 0.325$) and gender (chi-square value = 0.085, $p = 0.771$). Age Matching: Mean age for cases was 59.1 years ($SD = 13.74699$ years) and that for controls was 61.1 years ($SD = 14.90746$ years). No significant difference was noted in mean age among cases and controls. Gender Matching: Among cases, 37 (37%) were females and 63 (63%) were males; among the controls, 39 (39%) were females and 61 (61%) were males. No significant difference was noted between cases and controls in gender distribution.

Age categorization (Table 1): Age was grouped into clinically relevant categories (20–<40, 40–<50, 50–<60, ≥ 60 years). This grouping helped identify patterns across age ranges, though no significant association with CKD was observed (chi-square = 0.411, $p = 0.938$).

Result of Univariate analysis: Univariate analysis was done using the chi-square test between CKD and the variables under study (Table 1). Significant (unadjusted) associations were found between the risk of CKD and history of diabetes (chi-square = 15.126, $p < 0.01$), history of hypertension ($p < 0.01$, $\chi^2 = 31.202$), history of cardiovascular disease ($p < 0.01$, chi-square = 17.195) and family history of kidney disease ($p < 0.01$, chi-square = 8.791). On the other hand, the factors like the history of urinary tract infection, history of hypothyroidism did not show any significant association with CKD.

Results of multivariable analysis: Multivariable analysis was done using logistic regression for unadjusted associations considering the factors which showed associations in univariate analysis, while controlling for potential confounders (Table 2). Logistic regression was used to study matched variables and assess the independent effects of other variables. There was an insignificant association between CKD and history of diabetes mellitus (OR = 1.668, CI: 0.832–3.344, $p = 0.149$). However there were significant associations between CKD and history of hypertension (OR = 5.255, CI: 2.512–10.993, $p < 0.01$), history of cardiovascular disease (OR = 2.336, CI: 1.112–4.909, $p = 0.025$) and family history of kidney disease (OR = 7.359, CI: 1.902–28.476, $p = 0.004$). Subgroup analyses were not performed. There was no missing data; so, complete case and control analyses were done.

Table-1: Unadjusted associations between the variables under study with the risk of CKD

Variables	Cases (N=100)		Controls (N=100)		P- value & χ^2 value	
	No.	%	No.	%		
Gender	Female	37	37	39	39	P=0.771
	Male	63	63	61	61	$\chi^2=0.085$
Age group	20- 40	11	11	9	9	P=0.938 $\chi^2=0.411$
	41- 50	10	10	9	9	
	51-60	22	22	21	21	
	≥ 60	57	57	61	61	
History of diabetes	No	27	27	54	54	P<0.01
	Yes	73	73	46	46	$\chi^2=15.126$
History of hypertension	No	14	14	51	51	P<0.01
	Yes	86	86	49	49	$\chi^2=31.202$
History of urinary tract infection	No	74	74	85	85	P=0.054
	Yes	26	26	15	15	$\chi^2=3.712$
History of cardiovascular disease	No	56	56	83	83	P<0.01
	Yes	44	44	17	17	$\chi^2=17.195$
Family history of kidney disease	No	97	97	85	85	P=0.003
	Yes	3	3	15	15	$\chi^2=8.791$
History of hypothyroidism	No	84	84	83	83	P=0.849
	Yes	16	16	17	17	$\chi^2=0.036$

Table 2: Adjusted association between study variables and risk of CKD

Variables	OR (adjusted)	95% CI	P-value
History of diabetes	1.668	0.832- 3.344	0.149
History of hypertension	5.255	2.512- 10.993	<0.01
History of cardiovascular disease	2.336	1.112- 4.909	0.025
History of kidney disease	7.359	1.902- 28.476	0.004

The above approach ensured that both individual and combined effects of variables could be explored, identifying key predictors of CKD risk while noting potential confounders¹⁴.

Discussion

This study evaluated the presence or absence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) as the main outcome measure. The history of various contributory risk factors served as secondary outcome measures. Tests like Chi-square, odds ratios (ORs) and logistic regression were employed to elucidate the relationship between CKD and these variables.

In our study, out of 100 CKD cases 63 (50.8%) were males and 37 (48.7%) were female; in the control group, 61(49.2%) were males and 39 (51.3%) were female. The mean age for cases was 59.1 years as against 61.1 years for controls. The findings reinforce the multifactorial nature of CKD and its demographic and clinical determinants in South Kerala, providing valuable insights for prevention and management strategies. It highlighted the prevalence of hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and family history of kidney disease as critical contributors to CKD in the elderly population.

These findings are corroborated by a study on the epidemiology and contributing factors for chronic kidney disease from Odisha by Palo et al, where among 83 cases and 153 controls the mean age of the 83 cases was 49±10.62 years with 81.0% of cases male.¹⁴ A similar study by Ghelichi – Ghojogh et al to investigate the association of several behavioral and health-related

factors with CKD in the Iranian population the mean age of cases and controls were 59.6 ± 12.4 and 58.9 ± 12.2 respectively¹⁵. The study successfully identified and compared key risk factors associated with CKD.

Association with diabetes mellitus: A strong unadjusted association was found between CKD and a history of diabetes mellitus from this study, which is consistent with a study from Nepal which studied Diabetes mellitus as a Potential Risk Factor for Renal Disease, where diabetic patients had nearly twice the risk of CKD (Odds Ratio=1.97, $p=0.001$).¹⁶ Additionally, the START-India study found that more than 40% of individuals with type 2 diabetes had CKD, though most maintained relatively preserved renal function (eGFR >60 ml/min). This means that there are less limitations when choosing oral anti-diabetic medications.¹⁷ Supporting this, a study from Kerala by Soman et al. showed that the mean duration of diabetes in CKD patients was 121.92 months, compared to 92.72 months in non-CKD individuals. Random blood sugar levels were also significantly higher in CKD cases than controls (238.49 mg% versus 199.41 mg%).¹⁸ However, the adjusted association between CKD and diabetes mellitus was insignificant (OR= 1.668, CI: 0.832- 3.344, $p= 0.149$).

Association with Hypertension: A notable association (both unadjusted and adjusted) was found with Hypertension and CKD. This finding is comparable to a case control study done at district hospital of Indonesia by Indrayanti et al which showed that hypertension is a risk factor for CKD (odds ratio 11.50).¹⁹ Similar findings were observed from a cross sectional study among rural population in South India which determined that hypertension remained a significant risk factor for CKD, even after age, diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular risk factors were controlled for.(OR 2.22, 95% CI 1.46–3.36, $P<0.001$).²⁰ Similarly, a community study from North Kerala by Jacob et al, showed that diabetic nephropathy (44.6%), followed by hypertensive nephropathy (33.3%) were leading causes of CKD.⁸

Association with Cardiovascular Disease: A strong relationship (both adjusted and unadjusted) was also observed between CKD and cardiovascular disease, with an OR of 3.836 ($p = 0.0001$) ($\chi^2=17.195$). This finding highlights the interconnectedness of cardiovascular health and kidney function. However, this is in contrast with findings from a prospective cohort study by Lim et al which reported lower rates of cardiovascular disease (4.6%) in a CKD patient cohort with a median follow-up period of 4.3 years. As eGFR declined and albuminuria rose, the risks of CVD and all-cause death rose significantly (all p -trend <0.05)²¹. A study by Anand et al. to find out the prevalence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) in two major Indian cities and projections for associated cardiovascular disease suggests that individuals with CKD were more frequently classified as high-risk for cardiovascular events based on cardiovascular risk scores, compared to those without CKD.^{20, 22} Similarly, the above study by Jacob et al from North Kerala . Identified common co-morbidities in CKD patients, as diabetes (47.3%), cardiovascular disease (30.6%), hypertension (61.4%), malignancies (2.6%), retinopathy (28%), and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (10%). These findings highlight the complex interplay between CKD and various chronic conditions¹⁸.

Association with family history of kidney disease: There was a significant association between CKD and the history of previous kidney disease which highlights the importance of genetic factors in the development of kidney disease. This is in accordance with a study by Aregawi et al were patients with a family history of kidney diseases were more likely to have CKD than having no family history of kidney diseases.²³

Lack of Association with Urinary Tract Infections (UTIs) and Hypothyroidism: There was no association between CKD and a history of urinary tract infections (UTIs) in this study. Although the p -value was slightly above the conventional threshold for significance, this suggests a potential link worth further exploration. This is in contrast to a population-based case control study by Saucier et al in Minnesota which revealed that cases with CKD were significantly likely than controls to have a history of diabetes (41.5% vs 17.0%), hypertension (71.7% vs 49.1%), frequent UTIs (22.6% vs 6.6%), struvite stones (7.5% vs 0%), and allopurinol use (32.1% vs 4.7%)²⁴ while a meta-analysis of Urinary Tract Infections among Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease by Ahmed et al suggests that 80% of UTI resistance cases were recorded in CKD patients.²⁵

Our study showed no significant associations between CKD and hypothyroidism (OR=0.930) ($p=0.849$), indicating that hypothyroidism does not appear to influence the likelihood of developing CKD or previous kidney disease history odds ratio (OR=0.175) ($p=0.003$ suggesting that prior kidney disease does not increase the risk for CKD in this

sample. This is in contrast with a study by Lo et al, which reported a higher prevalence of hypothyroidism in persons with chronic kidney disease who had lower eGFR levels.²⁶

Limitations of the study

The study was done in a constrained resource setting, which posed several limitations.

Case control studies, while effective for identifying associations, do not establish causality. Being retrospective in nature, the relationship between CKD and risk factors like hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and family history of kidney disease cannot be absolutely established. The study was conducted on a limited sample size of 100 cases and controls and at a single tertiary care hospital in South Kerala, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions or healthcare settings. A larger sample size could improve statistical power and the ability to detect smaller differences in risk factors or subgroup analyses. This could introduce residual confounding in the multivariable model. The study did not account for the stage of CKD in participants or for patients with GFR near the cutoffs, which could have provided granularity into how different risk factors influence CKD progression and severity. The study did not account for medication use, including use of nephrotoxic drugs, which could impact kidney function and confound associations with CKD. The study focused on clinical risk factors (e.g., hypertension, cardiovascular disease) and family history, but did not extensively investigate modifiable lifestyle factors (e.g., diet, physical activity, smoking) or biomarkers such as inflammatory markers or urinary albumin levels, which could provide additional insights into the pathophysiology of CKD, that could contribute to CKD development. Information on the duration of CKD and comorbid conditions such as hypertension or diabetes was not collected, limiting an understanding of the temporal dynamics of risk factors and disease progression.

Recommendations

Given the study findings of significant association between hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and family history of kidney disease with CKD, it is recommended that healthcare systems implement routine screening for these risk factors, particularly among elderly populations. Future studies should investigate a broader range of potential risk factors, including lifestyle factors (e.g., diet, physical activity, smoking) and biomarkers, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the multifactorial nature of CKD. Additionally, reporting the stage of CKD in participants would provide further insights into the relationship between risk factors and disease severity, enabling more nuanced analyses and interventions.

This could help identify modifiable risks through early detection and management that can be targeted for prevention and help reduce the incidence and progression of CKD. Future research might assess the external validity of the associations observed in the current study by including multi-center or population-based data to help validate the findings across different regions, populations, and healthcare settings. It is crucial for future studies to clearly outline and implement strategies for overseeing missing data, to minimize bias that might arise from missing values, especially when working with large datasets. To better understand the causal relationships between risk factors and CKD, prospective cohort studies should be conducted. Targeted public health campaigns aimed at educating and creating awareness among people about the risks of uncontrolled hypertension and the importance of managing cardiovascular health may reduce the burden of CKD and can help prevent the progression to end-stage renal disease. By implementing these recommendations, we can improve our understanding of CKD risk factors, enhance early detection and intervention efforts, and reduce the burden of CKD, especially among vulnerable populations.

Conclusions

The findings of this study suggest significant associations between chronic kidney disease (CKD) and certain risk factors, particularly a history of hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and family history of kidney disease. However, the absence of significant findings for some variables (e.g., history of urinary tract infections) should be interpreted cautiously, and larger sampled studies or different methodologies may provide more clarity. While the sample size was adequate for a preliminary study conducted under constrained resources, regional differences in healthcare access, genetic predispositions, ethnicities, and environmental factors must be considered when generalizing these results.

In conclusion, the study offers important insights into the relationship between certain risk factors and CKD. Further research, with a larger, more diverse sample, and consideration of additional confounders, is needed to confirm these results and better understand the multifactorial causes of CKD.

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